

MODELING AND OPTIMIZATION OF PHOTO-FENTON DEGRADATION OF 124-TCB AT NEUTRAL PH CONDIIONES USING A VISIBLE LED SOURCE.

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Introduction

There is significant environmental concern about chlorinated organic compounds (COCs) in wastewater, surface water, and groundwater due to their low biodegradability and high persistence. Under the EU Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC), several COCs have been recently added to the list of substances to be monitored, encouraging limiting their production and use [1]. In this work, 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene (124-TCB) was selected as a model compound to study its abatement using the photo-Fenton process at neutral pH using ferrioxalate as catalyst source, which was enhanced with visible low energy consumption light-emitting diode (LED). A D-optimal design combined with response surface methodology (RSM) was combined to simultaneously evaluate the effect of the main reaction variables: hydrogen peroxide concentration (HP, 0.5 (61.5 ppm) to 5 (612 ppm) times the stoichiometric amount), iron dosage (Fe, 3-10 ppm), and radiation level (Rad, 0,1 Low and 0.15 Wcm⁻² High), on 124-TCB conversion ($X_{124-TCB}^{180\ min}$).

Material and Methods

The experiments were carried out in a double-walled cylindrical thermostat batch reactor (see Fig. 1, V_T=100 ml). The reaction mixture was illuminated with a Vis-LED lamp located at the top of the reactor (optical power output of up to 4.17 W at 470 nm). To prevent iron precipitation and maximize the fraction of radiation absorbed in the system, an Oxalate/Fe molar ratio of 10 was adopted [2]. For all tests, the 124-TCB initial concentration was the saturation one (28 ppm). The organic compounds were identified and quantified by GC/MS. The concentration of HP and Fe (Fe^T and Fe⁺²) were determined by colorimetric titration, using a spectrophotometer at 410 nm and 510 nm, respectively. Ionic organic by-products and chlorides were measured by IC. More details can be found in Lorenzo et al., 2021 [3].

Results and Discussion

RSM was performed to statistically evaluate the degradation of 124-TCB by a D-optimal design. Multiple regression analysis was used to calculate the model coefficients and the analysis of variance (ANOVA) with a 95% confidence level. Satisfactory values of R² (0.986) and adjusted R² (0.979 and 0.9993, respectively) were obtained for the model. Eqs. 1 and 2 represent the RSM models in actual terms that describe the $X_{124-TCB}^{180\ min}$ for each Rad level studied (M1: Low Rad, M2: High Rad). From the ANOVA results, both models (M1 and M2) can be characterized as statistically significant.

$$X_{124-TCB}^{180\ min}(M1) = 63.26 + 0.041 \cdot HP + 4.26 \cdot Fe - 0.000138 \cdot HP^2 \quad (Eq. 1)$$

$$X_{124-TCB}^{180\ min}(M2) = 66.65 + 0.042 \cdot HP + 4.27 \cdot Fe - 0.000137 \cdot HP^2 \quad (Eq. 2)$$

From these equations, it can be observed that larger Fe and HP values (terms with a positive sign) would result in higher $X_{124-TCB}^{180\ min}$. However, the concentration of the catalyst (Fe) being the term of greatest significance. On the other hand, the influence of the HP² term is negative since an excess of an oxidant agent produces a hydroxyl radical scavenging effect and accelerates its self-decomposition.

The response surface for M1 model is presented in Figure 2. First, note that for all the range of operating conditions studied, $X_{124-TCB}^{180\ min}$ higher than 45% were obtained. The minimum value was obtained for conditions of HP=612 ppm and Fe=3 ppm. Here the inhibitory effect (free radical trapping) is observed when using high doses of an oxidizing agent. On the other hand, the maximum $X_{124-TCB}^{180\ min}$ was reached for conditions of medium/high dose of catalyst (7/10 ppm Fe) and low/medium doses of oxidant agent (61.5/350 ppm HP). Similar behaviour was obtained using high levels of radiation ($I=0.15\ Wcm^{-2}$). However, for this Rad condition, the minimum $X_{124-TCB}^{180\ min}$ obtained was higher than 75%. Therefore, the significance of radiation in the process is highlighted.

Fig 1. Photograph of the employed photoreactor

Fig 2. Response Surface $X_{124-TCB}^{180\ min}$ versus HP and Fe concentration. Low Rad.

The experimental (Cl_{exp}^t) and stoichiometric (Cl_{stc}^t) chloride concentration were evaluated for different reaction conditions. For conditions of maximum 124-TCB conversion ($X_{124-TCB}^{180\ min} = 96.24\%$; $I=0.15\ Wcm^{-2}$, HP=305 ppm and Fe=5 ppm) the $Cl_{exp}^{180\ min} = 6\ ppm$ is lower than the $Cl_{stc}^{180\ min} = 15\ ppm$. Therefore, the total dechlorination of 124-TCB is not reached. These could be due to unidentified products or volatile chlorinated by-products [4]. It was only possible to obtain a better chloride balance for higher radiation doses. For conditions of $I=0.22\ Wcm^{-2}$, HP=305 ppm and Fe=5 ppm, a difference $Cl_{stc}^{t=180\ min} - Cl_{exp}^{t=180\ min} = 1.3\ ppm$ was obtained.

Conclusions

124-TCB could be successfully degraded under photo-Fenton conditions at neutral pH using ferrioxalate and a low energy consumption Vis-LED as the iron and the radiation source, respectively. To study the effects of the process parameters: HP, Fe and Rad; a D-optimal experimental design combined with response surface methodology was applied. Among the studied variables, it could be seen that the largest effect in 124-TCB conversion was due to Rad (the most significant term), followed by Fe, and finally the HP term.

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CERTIFICATE

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